

GENOMED4ALL

Transforming the response to Hematological Diseases by seizing the power of Artificial Intelligence

23 partners

8 countries

€10M in funding

An open hub for clinicians & researchers to work together defining, developing & validating AI models to improve the way we currently diagnose & treat HDs.

3 use cases in Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS), Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) & Multiple Myeloma (MM)

INNOVATION

INTEROPERABILITY

TRUST

SCALABILITY

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

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SYNTHEMA

Synthetic hematological data over federated computing networks

16 partners

10 countries

€7M in funding

A cross-border hub to develop & validate Artificial Intelligence techniques for anonymisation & synthetic data generation in rare hematological diseases.

2 use cases in Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) & Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)

VIRTUAL PATIENTS

PRIVACY BY-DESIGN

ETHICS & DATA PROTECTION

COLLABORATION IS KEY

Funded by the European Union

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